

Effect of Conservation of Energy on MB and Generalized Distributions

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Recently, many new distributions have appeared in the literature in addition to the Maxwell-Boltzmann, for example the Tsallis and Kaniadakis distributions among others. These are said to fit certain experimental data. There has also been a trend to link these new distributions to the maximization of a generalized entropy. In this note, we try to examine the importance of energy conservation in two particle collisions and the consequences of kinematics on the derivation of the equilibrium distribution.

Maxwell-Boltzmann Case

The Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution $C \exp(1/T(e) = \exp(1/T(e-u))$ where u is the chemical potential, may be obtained in various ways. First, however, consider the effects of the conservation of overall total energy E in a gas of N particles. In such a case, one may ask what is the average number of particles with energy $E_1 < E$? It seems it is:

$$N p(E_1) \text{ where } p \text{ is probability } ((1))$$

It seems that overall energy conservation immediately imposes a restriction on the distribution because the energy represented by ((1)) is $E_1 N p(E_1) \leq E$. If E_1 is a large number, close to E , then $N p(E_1)$ must be a small number, meaning $p(E_1)$ is very small for large E_1 . (Usually, normalization restrictions are used to argue a rapidly dropping $p(e)$.) Next, consider two particle collisions (which seems to be the approximation normally used in the literature). If the cross section is the same for different incoming particle energies, one may argue an "and" probability situation i.e.:

For incoming e_1 and e_2 , the probability is proportional to: $P(e_1)P(e_2)$.

For the sake of argument, imagine the emerging particles are e_3 and e_4 and there is no energy conservation even though there is equilibrium. It seems equilibrium implies time reversal, at the reaction level, otherwise there would be a difference between running a movie forward or backward (on average) which implies a direction in time i.e. time evolution i.e. no equilibrium. Thus:

$$P(e_1)P(e_2) = P(e_3)P(e_4) \quad ((1))$$

Taking the \ln of ((1)) leads to a conservation equation where $\ln(P(e))$ is a function of e . Thus, one has no choice but to accept the conservation of some function of e if one assumes ((1)). Physically, it seems choosing e (i.e. choosing an elastic collision) is the solution which makes sense. Alternatively, consider a different argument which does not involve the \ln . By overall energy conservation, it has been argued above the $P(e) \ll 1$ for large e . If there is no energy

conservation for e_1, e_2 changing into e_3, e_4 (i.e. there is some kind of energy pool which can absorb or distribute energy) then e_1 and e_2 values near E/N may collide to form e_3 and e_4 with very large energies, say near $E/2$. If ((1)) holds, then if $e_1=e_2$, this implies that $P(e_1)$ must be very close to $P(E/2)$, i.e. very small. Thus, $P(e)$ must be more or less constant and small for all N which means there is no energy distribution. Experiment, however, shows clear energy distributions.

Taking the \ln of ((1)) and linking the resulting conservation equation to conservation of energy immediately yields the Maxwell-Boltzmann (MB) equilibrium distribution (and is consistent with Boltzmann's transport equation).

Entropy Considerations

In the literature, however, there is an emphasis on obtaining the MB distribution by maximizing entropy subject to an energy constraint, where $-f \ln(f)$ is used as the entropy density i.e.

Maximize: $\int \text{phase space} -f \ln(f) - 1/T \int e f$ ((2))

Formally, such a "maximization" works, but we argue that due to the nature of the \ln function, ((2)) is really a construct for the equation: $\ln(f) = -1/T e$ which is the same result as taking the \ln of ((1)) and equating the resulting conservation equation to energy conservation. To see the property of \ln , consider:

$\ln(f+df) = \ln(f) + df/f$ Thus, multiplying by f means the second term on the RHS is df . If one insists f is normalized then: $\int \text{phase space} f = 1 = \int \text{phase space} f+df$ so $\int \text{phase space} df = 0$. Thus, in "varying" the entropy density $-f \ln(f)$, one is technically only varying f , but the constraint is of the form $-1/T \int e f$ so one is essentially stating: $\ln(f) = -1/T e$.

The point we wish to make is that this seems to be an unusual type of "maximization" as one maximizes A subject to constraint B and finds that the result is that $A=B$.

Generalized Distributions

Recently, there has been interest in generalized distributions. For these, one cannot have ((1)) because it leads to the MB distribution. Thus for equilibrium, different kinematical scenarios are needed. For example, in (1) it is suggested one use $G(f_1, f_3)$ where f_1 is the starting state and f_3 the arrival state. An example would be: $f_1(1-f_3)$, i.e. the fermion exclusion principle in quantum mechanics. Thus, for this example, one would have:

$$f_1(1-f_3) f_2(1-f_4) = f_3 (1-f_1) f_4 (1-f_2) \quad ((3))$$

One may notice the factorability of f . (What is a little unusual perhaps about $G(f_1, f_3)$ is it assumes f_1 changes into f_3 and f_2 into f_4 . If the particles are identical and the interaction zone a black box, it seems one does not know f_1 becomes f_3 . Nevertheless, one might perhaps consider two interactions f_1 to f_3 (f_2 to f_4) and f_1 to f_4 (f_2 to f_3 .) A solution to ((3)) is $f_i / (1-f_i)$

= Constant = .5 which is not a function of e. Another solution is $f_i / (1-f_i) = k(f_i)$ where k is an unknown function. For $k(f_i) = e_i$, one obtains energy conservation from ((3))

In (1), it is argued that instead of using f_i as in ((1)), one may use $G(f_i, f_i')$ where f_i is the starting state and f_i' the arrival state and G a function such that;

$$G(f_1, f_2) = a(f_1)b(f_2)c(f_1, f_2) \text{ where } c(f_1, f_2) = c(f_2, f_1) \quad ((4))$$

(It may be noted the assumption that $c(f_1, f_2)$ be symmetric essentially makes $G(f_1, f_2)$ separable i.e. $= a(f_1)b(f_2)$ with respect to the equilibrium situation because there is $G(f_1, f_2)$ on the LHS side of an equation and $G(f_2, f_1)$ on the RHS.)

With ((4)): $G(f_1, f_2) / G(f_2, f_1) = a(f_1)b(f_2) / [a(f_2)b(f_1)] = k(f_1) / k(f_2) \quad ((5))$ where $k(f_1) = a(f_1)/b(f_1)$.

Consider the example $G(f_1, f_2) = f_1(1-f_2)$. Then:

$f_1(1-f_2) / [f_2(1-f_1)] = k(f_1)/k(f_2)$ leads to: $k(f_i) = f_i / (1-f_i) \quad ((6))$ which was found above.

One may apply this argument to: e_1 changing to e_3 and e_2 changing to e_4 and the reverse situation:

$$G(f_1, f_3) G(f_2, f_4) = G(f_3, f_1) G(f_4, f_2) \text{ or } k(f_1) / k(f_3) = k(f_4) / k(f_2) \quad ((7))$$

Taking the ln of ((7)) yields a conservation equation:

$$\ln(k(f_1)) + \ln(k(f_2)) = \ln(k(f_3)) + \ln(k(f_4)) \quad ((8))$$

If one equates this to conservation of energy, then

$\ln(k(f_i)) = e_i$ or $\ln(k)$ is the inverse function of f , the distribution where the function k follows from the kinematics. ((9))

Again, assuming ((4)) forces conservation of energy in the reaction. To try to understand this, one may use similar arguments to those of the MB case. Imagine there are N particles and a total energy of E . Then, by the MB arguments $P(e) \ll 1$ if e is large because $NP(e)$ is the average number of particles with energy e , even in $P(e)$ is not an MB distribution. Next, assume there is no energy conservation in a reaction and that e_3 and e_4 are the same and very large. Then, f_3 and f_4 are tiny values, almost 0 so:

$G(f_1, 0) G(f_2, 0) = G(0, f_1) G(0, f_2)$ This would imply that $k(f_i) = k(0)$ or that all f_i are small and about the same which is a problem. Thus, it seems there must be conservation of energy in the reaction.

Entropy Considerations

With respect to maximization of entropy for generalized cases, it seems the following approach is used (see (1)):

First, entropy is written as $-k_B \int_{\text{phase space}} df \ln(k(f))$ i.e. an integration over df is introduced. Then, one takes d/df of $S - 1/T \int_{\text{phase space}} f(e-u)$ i.e. overall constant energy and particle number. For the S term, the integration over df cancels the derivative d/df operation, so:

$$\ln(k(f)) - 1/T (e-u)$$

Thus, f and $\ln(k)$ are inverse functions, which is identical to the conservation of energy approach. Thus, it seems the entropy approach is a math construct to “create” the result of f being the inverse function of $\ln(k)$ where k is a function related to kinematics. It seems the function-inverse function result follows directly from kinematics and conservation of energy as the “maximization” process seems to be unusual (i.e. integrate and then differentiate so the two operations cancel).

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that for the MB and more generalized equilibrium distribution cases, energy conservation and reaction kinematics (i.e. reaction probabilities based on functions of the distribution) seem to be key to deriving the distribution. The maximization of entropy seems to be a mathematical construct designed to obtain the same result.

References

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